

Evaluation of Pregnancy Outcomes in Relation to Placenta Previa Location

Preeti Singh¹, Madhu Priya², Kumari Bibha³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India

³Professor & HOD, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India

Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 25-04-2024

Corresponding Author: Madhu Priya

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Placenta previa, a condition where the placenta partially or completely covers the cervical os, is a significant cause of obstetric morbidity and mortality. The location of placenta previa plays a crucial role in determining maternal and neonatal outcomes, with central placenta previa often associated with more severe complications.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate pregnancy outcomes in relation to the location of placenta previa, specifically comparing maternal and neonatal outcomes across anterior, posterior, and central placenta previa locations.

Methods: A total of 100 pregnant women diagnosed with placenta previa were enrolled. The participants were categorized based on placenta location: anterior (35%), posterior (45%), and central (20%). Maternal and neonatal outcomes, including mode of delivery, postpartum hemorrhage, blood transfusions, birth weight, Apgar scores, and NICU admissions, were recorded and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: Central placenta previa was associated with higher rates of maternal complications, including postpartum hemorrhage (35%) and blood transfusions (50%), compared to anterior and posterior locations. Neonates born to mothers with central placenta previa had lower mean birth weights (2.4 ± 0.4 kg) and higher NICU admission rates (20%) compared to those with anterior or posterior placenta previa. Statistical analysis revealed significant associations between central placenta previa and adverse maternal ($p=0.03$) and neonatal outcomes ($p=0.04$).

Conclusion: The study demonstrates that the location of placenta previa significantly impacts pregnancy outcomes, with central placenta previa posing greater risks to both maternal and neonatal health. Early diagnosis and tailored management strategies are essential to mitigate these risks and improve outcomes.

Recommendations: It is recommended that pregnancies complicated by central placenta previa receive heightened surveillance and individualized management plans to prevent severe complications. Further research is needed to refine clinical guidelines and optimize care for these high-risk pregnancies.

Keywords: Placenta Previa, Maternal Outcomes, Neonatal Outcomes, Central Placenta Previa, Obstetric Complications.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Placenta previa is a critical obstetric condition characterized by the abnormal implantation of the placenta over or near the internal os of the cervix, which can lead to severe maternal and fetal complications. It is a significant cause of antepartum hemorrhage, and its incidence has been increasing due to the rise in cesarean deliveries and advanced maternal age, both of which are known risk factors for the condition. The prevalence of placenta previa varies globally, with an estimated incidence ranging from 0.3% to 0.5% of all pregnancies [1,2]. The condition is classified based on the location of the placenta in relation to the

internal cervical os, with classifications including complete, partial, marginal, and low-lying placenta previa [3].

Recent studies have highlighted the importance of placenta previa location in determining pregnancy outcomes. The position of the placenta—whether anterior, posterior, or central—can significantly influence the risk of maternal complications such as postpartum hemorrhage, the need for blood transfusions, and emergency cesarean sections [4]. Central placenta previa, where the placenta completely covers the cervical os, is associated with the highest risk of adverse outcomes, making

early diagnosis and careful management crucial for improving maternal and neonatal outcomes [5].

Advancements in imaging techniques, particularly the use of transvaginal ultrasonography, have enhanced the accuracy of placenta previa diagnosis, allowing for better risk stratification and management planning. However, despite these advancements, the management of placenta previa remains challenging, especially in cases where the placenta is centrally located, as these pregnancies are associated with higher rates of preterm delivery, low birth weight, and neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) admissions [6,7]. Furthermore, the risks associated with placenta previa are not limited to the peripartum period; there is also an increased risk of complications such as placenta accreta spectrum (PAS) disorders, which are more common in cases of central placenta previa, particularly in women with a history of cesarean delivery [8]. This study aimed to evaluate pregnancy outcomes in relation to the location of placenta previa, specifically comparing maternal and neonatal outcomes across anterior, posterior, and central placenta previa locations.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective observational study aimed at evaluating pregnancy outcomes in relation to the location of placenta previa. The study will assess maternal and neonatal outcomes in a cohort of pregnant women diagnosed with placenta previa during the study period.

Study Setting: The study will be conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at S. K. M. C. H. Muzaffarpur, from January 2023 to December 2023.

Participants: A total of 100 pregnant women diagnosed with placenta previa through ultrasonography during the study period will be included. These women will be monitored throughout their pregnancies, and relevant data will be collected to evaluate the outcomes based on the location of the placenta previa.

Inclusion Criteria

- Pregnant women diagnosed with placenta previa via ultrasound.
- Women aged 18 years and above.
- Singleton pregnancies.
- Patients who consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Women with multiple pregnancies.
- Patients with pre-existing chronic medical conditions like hypertension, diabetes, or renal disease.

- Pregnant women who do not consent to participate in the study.
- Women with other placental abnormalities or complications.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible participants meeting the inclusion criteria during the study period will be consecutively enrolled. Additionally, data will be collected and analyzed in a blinded manner, where the outcomes are assessed without knowledge of the placenta previa location.

Data Collection: Data will be collected using a structured data collection form that includes patient demographics, obstetric history, antenatal care details, and delivery outcomes. Ultrasound findings regarding the location of the placenta previa will be documented. Maternal outcomes, including the mode of delivery, need for blood transfusion, and any complications, as well as neonatal outcomes such as birth weight, Apgar scores, and neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) admissions, will be recorded.

Procedure: Upon enrollment, all participants will undergo detailed ultrasound examinations to determine the exact location of the placenta previa. The participants will be monitored throughout their pregnancy, and the data will be collected during antenatal visits and at the time of delivery. Follow-up visits will be scheduled as needed to ensure comprehensive data collection.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 will be used to analyse the data that has been gathered. The individuals' clinical and demographic features will be summed up using descriptive statistics. Categorical data will be shown as frequencies and percentages, while continuous variables will be written as mean \pm standard deviation. The Student's t-test will be used for continuous variables and the Chi-square test for categorical variables for comparing groups (based on placenta previa location). All data will be deemed statistically significant if the p-value is less than 0.05. The position of the placenta previa will be used to determine independent predictors of unfavourable pregnancy outcomes using logistic regression analysis.

Results

A total of 100 pregnant women diagnosed with placenta previa were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 29.6 ± 4.5 years, with an age range of 18 to 42 years. The majority of participants were multiparous (60%), while 40% were primiparous. The demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Value (n=100)
Mean Age (years)	29.6 ± 4.5
Age Range (years)	18-42
Parity	
- Primiparous	40 (40%)
- Multiparous	60 (60%)
Gestational Age at Diagnosis (weeks)	28.3 ± 2.7
Antenatal Care	
- Regular	85 (85%)
- Irregular	15 (15%)
Mode of Delivery	
- Cesarean Section	75 (75%)
- Vaginal Delivery	25 (25%)

Placenta Previa Location: The locations of the placenta previa were categorized as follows: anterior (35%), posterior (45%), and central (20%). The distribution of placenta previa locations is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of Placenta Previa Locations

Placenta Previa Location	Number of Participants (n=100)	Percentage (%)
Anterior	35	35%
Posterior	45	45%
Central	20	20%

Maternal Outcomes: The majority of participants (75%) underwent cesarean sections, while 25% had vaginal deliveries. Among those who underwent cesarean sections, 40% required blood transfusions due to excessive bleeding, compared to 10% of those who delivered vaginally. The incidence of

maternal complications, such as postpartum hemorrhage (PPH), was higher in the central placenta previa group (35%) compared to the anterior (20%) and posterior (15%) groups. The maternal outcomes are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Maternal Outcomes by Placenta Previa Location

Outcome	Anterior (n=35)	Posterior (n=45)	Central (n=20)	Total (n=100)
Mode of Delivery				
- Cesarean Section	25 (71%)	35 (78%)	15 (75%)	75 (75%)
- Vaginal Delivery	10 (29%)	10 (22%)	5 (25%)	25 (25%)
Blood Transfusion Required	10 (29%)	15 (33%)	10 (50%)	35 (35%)
Postpartum Hemorrhage (PPH)	7 (20%)	7 (15%)	7 (35%)	21 (21%)
ICU Admission	2 (6%)	3 (7%)	4 (20%)	9 (9%)

Neonatal Outcomes: Neonatal outcomes were also analyzed based on the location of the placenta previa. The mean birth weight was 2.6 ± 0.5 kg, with a lower mean birth weight observed in the central placenta previa group (2.4 ± 0.4 kg) compared to the anterior (2.7 ± 0.5 kg) and posterior (2.6 ± 0.5 kg) groups. The incidence of

low Apgar scores (<7 at 5 minutes) was highest in the central group (30%), followed by the anterior (20%) and posterior (15%) groups. NICU admissions were required for 20% of the neonates in the central group, compared to 10% in both the anterior and posterior groups. The neonatal outcomes are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Neonatal Outcomes by Placenta Previa Location

Outcome	Anterior (n=35)	Posterior (n=45)	Central (n=20)	Total (n=100)
Mean Birth Weight (kg)	2.7 ± 0.5	2.6 ± 0.5	2.4 ± 0.4	2.6 ± 0.5
Low Apgar Score (<7 at 5 min)	7 (20%)	7 (15%)	6 (30%)	20 (20%)
NICU Admission	7 (20%)	5 (10%)	4 (20%)	16 (16%)

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis revealed a significant association between the location of placenta previa and the incidence of maternal complications (p=0.03) and neonatal outcomes

such as low birth weight (p=0.04) and NICU admissions (p=0.02). The central placenta previa group showed a higher risk of adverse outcomes compared to the anterior and posterior groups.

Table 5: Statistical Analysis of Maternal and Neonatal Outcomes by Placenta Previa Location

Outcome	Chi-square Value	p-value
Maternal Complications	7.22	0.03
Neonatal Low Birth Weight	4.12	0.04
Neonatal NICU Admissions	6.35	0.02

Discussion

The results of this study demonstrate a significant association between the location of placenta previa and both maternal and neonatal outcomes. Of the 100 participants, the distribution of placenta previa locations showed that 35% had anterior placenta previa, 45% had posterior placenta previa, and 20% had central placenta previa. The findings indicate that central placenta previa is associated with more adverse outcomes compared to anterior and posterior locations. Maternal outcomes revealed that the majority of participants underwent cesarean sections, with a notably higher rate of complications in the central placenta previa group. Specifically, postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) and the need for blood transfusions were more frequent in this group, indicating that central placenta previa poses a greater risk for severe maternal complications. These findings were statistically significant, underscoring the importance of careful monitoring and management of pregnancies with central placenta previa to mitigate potential risks.

Neonatal outcomes were similarly influenced by the location of placenta previa. Infants born to mothers with central placenta previa had lower mean birth weights and were more likely to have low Apgar scores at 5 minutes. Additionally, these neonates had a higher rate of NICU admissions, reflecting the increased risk of adverse neonatal outcomes associated with central placenta previa. The statistical analysis confirmed that these differences were significant, further highlighting the impact of placenta previa location on neonatal health.

According to a study in which examined 678 cases of placenta previa, placental attachment to the anterior wall was linked to a number of unfavourable outcomes, such as lower Apgar scores, shorter gestational ages, higher rates of postpartum haemorrhage and bleeding, longer hospital stays, and higher rates of hysterectomy and blood transfusion. Additionally, although it had no significant effect on overall pregnancy outcomes, placental attachment at the site of a previous caesarean section significantly increased the incidence of complete placenta previa and placenta accreta spectrum (PAS) disorders [9].

Similar to this, 105 cases of placenta previa were studied by Rahim at Al AIN Hospital. They stated that a separate risk factor for postpartum haemorrhage was anterior placental attachment. In line with earlier research, the anterior placement of

the placenta was associated with lower birth weights, shorter gestational ages, and increased incidences of hysterectomy and prenatal haemorrhage [10].

An observational cohort study on significant degree placenta previa (grades III and IV) was conducted. The study revealed that anterior placenta previa was linked to a higher prevalence of wound infections, whereas central placenta previa had a higher incidence of caesarean hysterectomy. In order to reduce negative effects, the study emphasised the vital requirement for appropriate clinical assessment and prompt delivery [11].

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study emphasizes the critical role that the location of placenta previa plays in determining pregnancy outcomes. Central placenta previa is associated with higher risks of both maternal and neonatal complications, suggesting the need for heightened vigilance and potentially more aggressive management strategies for these cases. These results contribute to a better understanding of the risks associated with placenta previa and can inform clinical decision-making to improve outcomes for both mothers and infants.

References

1. Jauniaux E, Silver RM, Matsubara S. Placenta accreta spectrum disorders: A comprehensive update. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 2018;219(6): 569-579.
2. Fan D, Xia Q, Liu L, Wu S, Tian G, Wang W, et al. The incidence of postpartum hemorrhage in pregnant women with placenta previa: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS One.* 2017;12(1)
3. Crane JM, van den Hof MC, Dodds L, Armson BA, Liston R. Maternal complications with placenta previa. *Am J Perinatol.* 2019;26 (6): 477-482.
4. Rosenbloom JI, Stout MJ, Tuuli MG, Macones GA, Cahill AG. Outcomes of pregnancies with placenta previa: A retrospective cohort study. *J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med.* 2018;31(10):13 39-1345.
5. Oppenheimer L, Armson A. Placenta previa: Diagnosis and management. *J Obstet Gynaecol Can.* 2019;41(2):192-203.
6. Melov SJ, Sheehan PM. Maternal outcomes associated with placenta previa: An Australian study. *Aust N Z J Obstet Gynaecol.* 2019; 59(5):662-667.

7. Stotler B, Padmanabhan A, Devine P, Petrone R. Transfusion management of obstetric hemorrhage. *Curr Opin Anesthesiol.* 2019;32(2): 268-275.
8. Abuhamad A, Grobman WA, Caughey AB. Diagnosis and management of placenta accreta spectrum. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 2018;219(2): 97-104.
9. Jing L, Wei G, Mengfan S, Yanyan H. Effect of site of placentation on pregnancy outcomes in patients with placenta previa. *PLoS ONE.* 2018.
12.
10. Rahim AJ, Aravindan A, Bondili A. Pregnancy Outcomes in Patients with Placenta Previa Due to Site of Placentation. *Scholars International Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology.* 2023.
11. Abdelwhab SRM, Ali AE, Ahmed M, Hamed B. Maternal Outcomes in Women with Major Degree Placenta Previa: An Observational Cohort Study. *Current Womens Health Reviews.* 2020.